

SOCIAL SCIENCES

FACTORS INFLUENCING OLDER PEOPLE'S PERCEPTION OF THE MEANING OF LIFE: SOCIAL WORKERS' VIEWS

Virbaliėnė A.
Jezukeviėienė E.
Šiurienė A.
Riėytė V.

*Department of Nursing and Social Welfare, Faculty of Health Sciences
Klaipėdos valstybinė kolegija / Higher Education Institution, Klaipėda, Lithuania
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14236927>*

Abstract

The aging population and the increasing number of elderly people mean, older people face a variety of problems: changing health, past events and losses, narrowing of social ties, changes in social roles, negative social attitudes and personal characteristics. Old age is the last stage of a person's life, which is conducive to self-fulfilment and is synonymous with self-care, and it is important for a person to feel that his or her life still has a sense of purpose in order to live a more active and productive life, in a way that takes into account the person and the possibilities available to him or her.

Keywords: Old people, self-fulfillment, meaning of life.

INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the research topic. The world today is full of scientific advances and new inventions that are impacting human well-being and contributing to increased life expectancy (Toliuėienė and Virbalis, 2021). Bar-Tur (2021) highlights data collected by the World Health Organisation showing that the number of people aged over 60 is growing faster than in any other age group in most countries around the world. Old age is the last stage of a person's life, favourable for self-fulfilment and identified with self-care, so it is important for a person to feel that his or her life still has a meaning, which will help him or her to live a more active and productive life in a way that takes into account the person and the possibilities available to him or her (Mikulionienė, Rapolienė, Valaviėienė, 2018, Koropetska, 2014). In old age, time can be used for favourite and meaningful activities: it can be a source of development, new experiences, peace, joy or even finances, and it can help to reduce loneliness and find meaning in life (Charenkova, 2017). Grouden and Jose (2015) underline Viktor Frankl's assertion that the main human concern and psychological need is to search for and find meaning in life. The meaning and goals of life are unique to the individual, but this can be influenced by various external factors.

Research questions:

1. What factors influence the self-fulfilment and the search for meaning in life of the elderly?
2. What are the sources of meaning in life for the elderly?

Aim of the article. To identify the factors influencing the meaning of life for the elderly.

Research methods. Scientific literature analysis, semi-structured interviews, qualitative content analysis.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Type of research. In order to reveal the self-fulfilment of the elderly in their search for meaning in life, a qualitative type of data collection was used, and the research method was a semi-structured interview. The research is based on the attitudes, personal attitudes and everyday life of the research participants (Gaižauskaitė & Valaviėienė, 2016). The study was conducted in May 2024.

Sample. The research sample was based on the criterion of purposive sampling - social workers. Social workers working in care homes and day care centres were selected and participated in the study. The sample consisted of 6 social workers working with elderly people.

Research instrument. Semi-structured interview questions focused on 2 categories. The first category of questions contains 5 questions that focus on the factors of self-fulfilment and the search for the meaning of life in old age. The second category consists of 5 questions to uncover the sources of meaning in life for the elderly.

Research ethics. The ethical principles of the study were respected: free choice to participate, goodwill, confidentiality.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The meaning of life in old age. The results of the study highlighted the individuality of the concept of meaning of life. The concept of meaning in life consists of having a purpose, personal aspirations and desires, the actualization of meaning and the analysis of past events in relation to the present (see Table 1).

Table 1

Meaning of life in old age	
Category	Subcategory
Making sense of life in old age	Having a purpose
	Personal ambitions and desires
	Actualising meaning
	Analysing the past

Having a purpose in life is an essential component of living a meaningful life (Chindankutty and Dhanalakshmi, 2022). The results of this study revealed that meaning in life consists of having a purpose, individual aspirations and desires of the elderly person, and analysing and actualising the past. Foreign authors (Martela, Steger, 2016) point out that the meaningfulness of an older person's life is influenced by three important components: making sense of life experiences, the realisation of the most worthwhile goals, and the feelings of happiness and satisfaction that accompany

the achievement of goals

Barriers to the fulfilment of the older person. The results of the study showed that certain life events become barriers to finding meaning in life in old age. Not only the elderly person's own negative attitudes, negative feelings towards him or herself, negative attitudes towards him or her in society, and all the accumulated painful experiences that have influenced the negativity-based approach to life, but also changing or deteriorating health conditions (see Table 2).

Table 2

Barriers to the fulfilment of the elderly

Category	Subcategory
Life events	Losses
	Being alone
Negative personal feelings	Apathy
	Anger
	Fear
Negative public attitudes towards older people	Eidjism
	Stigmatisation
Personal lifetime experiences	Post-war period
	Lack of opportunities for improvement
Personal human characteristics characterised by negativity	Lack of desire
	Negative self-evaluation
	Negative attitude
	Closure
	Insufficiency
Deteriorating personal health status	Physical health
	Cognitive skills

The results of the study showed that certain life events become obstacles for older people in their search for meaning in life. Thus, this stage is still classified as a period of loss, in which the elderly person experiences concerns and problems that are unique to this stage, which include biological, cognitive, psychological, economic and social aspects of the person (Li, C., Jiang, Li, N. & Zhang, 2018). The results of this study revealed that bereavement is one of the most impactful events in the lives of older persons. It is also strongly influenced by the person's own negative feelings of apathy, loneliness, anger and fear. Older people also face stigmatisation and ageism in society, which contributes to social exclusion. The person himself changes and his

negative characteristics such as negative self-esteem, a negative attitude towards life, self-containedness and lack of independence become apparent. In the last stage of life, vital energy and physical resources decrease and health status changes (Bagdonas, Kairys, Zamalijeva, 2017; Mahalakshmi and Velusamy, 2017).

The main life goals that give meaning to life for older people are. The study shows that self-discovery in new activities, maintaining a close relationship with one's family, and faith are the most important factors in the goals that give meaning to an older person's life (see Table 3).

Table 3

Key life goals that give older people meaning in life

Category	Subcategory
Goals that give life meaning	Self-discovery in new activities
	Close links with family
	Belief

The meaning and goals of life are unique to the individual, but can be influenced by certain external factors (Charenkova, 2018). This study revealed that an older person's goals depend on their perception of the meaning of their life, what is important to them, and what their goals are based on. Three key goals are identified: self-discovery in new activities, close contact with family and faith. Foreign authors argue that family presence, personal development, religiosity and spirituality constitute the goals of the elderly (Grouden and Jose, 2015).

The influence of the interaction of the immediate environment on the meaning of life of the elderly. The results obtained from the study revealed that the family can both positively and negatively influence the meaningfulness of life of an elderly person. The positive influence of the family revealed links with the creation of new social roles, family care, motivation, support and a sense of security. On the other hand, negative associations with family can make a person feel helpless, abandoned and deprived of meaning in life (see Table 4).

Table 4

The impact of immediate environmental interactions on the meaning of life for older people

Category	Subcategory
Positive contribution of the family	New social roles
	Carefulness
	Motivation for action
	Support
	Safety
Negative contribution of the family	Helplessness
	Loss of the joy of life
	Abandoned

The results of the study revealed the influence of the interaction of the immediate environment on the elderly person's sense of life: the positive and negative contribution of the family. The positive contribution of the family is manifested in the creation of new social roles, caring, family support motivates the elderly person to act, and makes him/her feel safe and loved. Foreign authors argue that the involvement of family members in the older person's life, their acceptance and interpersonal relationships have a very significant impact on the meaning of the person's life (Grouden and Jose, 2015). If the relationship with relatives is not good, the elderly person feels helpless and abandoned and loses

the meaning of life. The old person feels humiliated, and is not looked up to by his or her children, or does not interact at all (Mahalakshmi and Velusamy, 2017).

Engagement of the elderly. The results of the study revealed general occupation, which highlighted the following favourite activities: artistic activities, sports, handicrafts, group activities, daily activities and events. It also revealed the benefits of engagement for older people in terms of participation, fulfilment, a sense of empowerment and usefulness, independence, routines and health (see Table 5).

Table 5

Engagement of the elderly

Category	Subcategory
General activities	Artistic activity
	Sport
	Handicrafts
	Group activities
	Daily activities
	Events
Benefits of engagement activities for the individual	Participation
	Self-realisation

	Enabling
	Self-sufficiency
	Establishing a routine
	Feeling useful
	Improving health

Engagement in old age is very important and necessary, and depends to a large extent on a person's abilities and interests. Activities are usually carried out in a shared setting, in group activities, according to the needs of the group gathered. This study has revealed the activities that give the most pleasure to the elderly person, which were: artistic activities, sports, handicrafts, group activities, events and daily activities. The more varied and individualised the activity, the more significant it is in increasing a person's self-esteem, helping them to cope with difficulties in their environment in order to achieve their personal dreams, and positively influencing their life satisfaction, which also affects their quality of life (Vosyliūtė, 2022). The self-expression of the elderly person in engagement activities is divided into two areas. The first one is activities linked to physical activity. The second is artistic self-expression, which is expressed through dancing, singing, making handicrafts and reading (Vosyliūtė, 2022). The study also revealed the benefits of engagement activi-

ties for older people, which consist in the self-fulfilment of the individual through participation in active activities. The elderly person establishes a daily routine, feels empowered, independent, included in the community, useful, needed and proud of themselves. Engagement activities also improve the person's health and support cognitive and perceptual functions. Foreign authors note that participation in various activities has a positive impact on the physical health of the elderly person, promotes the strengthening of motor and cognitive functions, and reduces the risk of dementia and mortality (Charenkova, 2017).

The importance of community activities and social ties for the meaning of life for old people.

Participants in the study revealed that involvement in community activities creates opportunities for socialising, developing social ties and can be a means to achieve meaning in their lives. Community with peers leads to the development of close relationships, thus providing a sense of security (see Table 6).

Table 6

The importance of community activities and social contacts for the meaning of life of the elderly

Category	Subcategory
The importance of community activities and social ties for the meaning of life	Communication opportunities
	A tool for finding meaning in life
	Safety
	Close relations
	Community with peers

Engaging in community activities, joining specific groups of people, promoting activities and social inclusion of the individual, creates opportunities for networking and bringing people closer together. As a result, the elderly person feels satisfaction in making sense of his or her relationship with the newly formed social world (Seidamirova and Shiuriene, 2023). This study revealed that fostering community activities and social relationships contributes to the elderly person's quest for meaning, a sense of fullness and security, self-discovery and self-improvement in the presence of peers.

CONCLUSIONS

1. In the last phase of life, the elderly person faces the tensions of generativity and stagnation, which oblige him or her to leave something behind for future generations. The pursuit of this goal encourages reflection in old age, which analyses the feelings associated with existential continuity, embracing the purpose and meaning of life, and looking for opportunities to make a meaningful impact on the world through one's strengths. A person's self-fulfilment and meaning in life are influenced by factors

that are individual to each person, related to the person's own character, health, past events, losses, social relationships, changes in social roles and often negative societal perceptions. The study reveals additional factors influencing self-actualisation, i.e. negative personal characteristics, negative feelings, different life experiences and losses. Once a person has clarified his or her concept of the meaning of life, he or she begins to strive for inner harmony, maturity in the relationship between the self and the world, and a reflective perception of the world.

2. Each person has inexhaustible resources based on spirituality and humanity, which help to achieve meaning through the proper reorientation of personal values and ideals towards particularly meaningful life goals, by responsibly linking the past to the future, and by honestly exercising faith, a sense of humour, creativity and love for oneself, others and the world. The components of older people's sources of meaning are usually family, friends, altruism, work, religion or spiritual practice, self-fulfilment, volunteering, engagement. These various sources contribute to the construction of meaning in the lives of older people by

stimulating their activity, communication and self-expression.

References:

1. Bagdonas, A., Kairys, A., Zamalijeva, O. (2017). Senų žmonių funkcionavimo, senatvės ir senėjimo tyrimų gairės: biopsichosocialinio modelio prieiga. *Socialinė teorija, empirija, politika ir praktika*, (15), 80-102.
2. Bar-Tur, L. (2021). Fostering well-being in the elderly: Translating theories on positive aging to practical approaches. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 8, 1-9.
3. Charenkova, J. (2017). Laisvalaikis ar laisvas laikas? Globos įstaigose gyvenančių vyresnio amžiaus asmenų patirtis. *Socialinė teorija, empirija, politika ir praktika*, 15, 103-119.
4. Charenkova, J. (2018). Vyresnio amžiaus asmenų persikėlimo į socialinės globos įstaigą patirtis: literatūros apžvalga. *Socialinė teorija, empirija, politika ir praktika*, 17, 21-36.
5. Chindankutty, N. V., & Dhanalakshmi, D. (2022). Healthy Ageing among Elderly from a Eudaimonic Viewpoint: A Conceptual Approach. *Indian Journal of Health & Wellbeing*, 13(2). 232-236.
6. Gaižauskaitė, I., Valavičienė, N. (2016). *Socialinių tyrimų metodai: kokybinis interviu*. Vilnius: VĮ Registrų centras.
7. Grouden, M. E., Jose, P. E. (2015). Do sources of meaning differentially predict search for meaning, presence of meaning, and wellbeing. *International journal of wellbeing*, 5(1), 33-52.
8. Koropetska, O. (2014). The social exclusion as a problem of self-realization of the elderly. *Journal of Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University*, 1(2-3), 267-275.
9. Li, C., Jiang, S., Li, N., Zhang, Q. (2018). Influence of social participation on life satisfaction and depression among Chinese elderly: Social support as a mediator. *Journal of community psychology*, 46(3), 345-355.
10. Mahalakshmi, M., Velusamy, M. (2017). Geriatric Psychological Problems: An Overview. *International Journal of Innovative Knowledge Concepts*, 5(5), 41-45.
11. Martela, F., Steger, M. F. (2016). The three meanings of meaning in life: Distinguishing coherence, purpose, and significance. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 11(5), 531-
12. Mikulionienė, S., Rapolienė, G., Valavičienė, N. (2018). *Vyresnio amžiaus žmonės, gyvenimas po vieną ir socialinė atskirtis*. Vilnius: Lietuvos socialinių tyrimų centras.
13. Seidamirova, S., Šiurienė, A. (2023). Senyvo amžiaus žmonių, gyvenančių namuose, socialinių ryšių pokyčiai. *Verslas, technologijos, biomedicina: inovacijų žvalgos 2023: straipsnių rinkinys*, (1), 279-289.
14. Toliušienė, V., Virbalis, T. (2021). Senyvo amžiaus asmenų adaptacijos procesas globos namuose. *Verslas, technologijos, biomedicina: inovacijų žvalgos 2021: straipsnių rinkinys*, (1), 523-533.